

Communication methods

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The concepts of communication vary according to the applicable divisions, including the division according to language (verbal - non-verbal), including the division according to size (subjective - personal - collective - public - middle - mass), including the division according to the industrial style (old - new), and according to the humanities (media - self - management), and the division may be according to the communication style as usual with the administrative aspect (vertical - horizontal - Qatari), and other innumerable divisions, and before identifying these divisions, we must know the keys by which these divisions are known and knowledge of the pillars of communication, so when we discuss these communication elements in order to reach effective communication, we should know the extent of interest in the future for all other communication elements, as follows¹:

- 1- The sender: The importance of the receiver is equal to the importance of the sender in the communication process. He listens, thinks, reacts and responds.
- 2- Message: The effect of the message is not known unless it is known who the receiver is, and how he interacts with the sender.
- 3- Method: The evaluation of the method is known from the extent to which it is listened to and responsive to the future.
- 4- Feedback: It is not known unless the receiver understands all the elements of communication.

We will later expand on the knowledge of each of these pillars in terms of the importance of the other pillars, their relationship to them, and the functions of each of them.

The word communication in Latin means common, and in English it means the common, familiar, and reciprocal thing between people. Thus, it can be said that the word communication means a process of transferring and exchanging information between people to achieve a goal.

¹ See: Means of communication: 37.

As for the researchers' definitions of the communication process, the most prominent of which is the definition of Karl Hofland, who said: Communication is the process through which the communicator provides stimuli to modify the behavior of other individuals.

As for Jihan Rashti, she says that communication is the process by which the recipient and sender of the message - living beings, humans or machines - interact in certain social contents, and in which ideas and information (stimuli) are transmitted between individuals about a specific issue, meaning or reality. Communication is based on sharing mental images and opinions².

Both researchers in management science (Al-Ameri and Al-Ghali, 2010) define it as communication: It is the process of transmitting and transmitting information from one person to another through sending and receiving symbols with meanings related to specific objectives that include asking others to follow a procedure, modify behavior, or any other matters.

In sociology, the scientist Charles Cooley believes that communication is the mechanism through which human relationships exist and mental symbols grow and develop by means of spreading these symbols across space and continuing through time.

From all these definitions, the communication process aims to gain support and persuasion, transfer and exchange information, provide a positive organizational climate, and enhance cooperation and coordination.

Dr. Fadil Delew points out that there are specialized definitions of "communication science", including the definition of Xavi Berger (it is the science that studies the production, processing and impact of symbols and signaling systems through analyzable theories, containing legitimate generalizations that enable the interpretation of phenomena related to production, processing and effects)³.

² - Consider: Communication and its contemporary theories: 25.

³ - See: History of Media and Communication: 14

Ross model⁴

Ross developed this model in 1965. Ross explains that the communication process is influenced by the feelings, attitudes and information of both the sender (source - interpreter) and the receiver (message analyst and interpreter). If the message sent is inaccurate, the receiver cannot interpret it and even understand it accurately. This is because the message to the receiver is different from the original message sent by the sender. As for the channels of communication, they are represented by the main channels of the senses of a healthy person, which are "auditory-visual-emotional (feeling)", and the message is in the form of (symbols- language - sound) feelings of information trends, symbols of sound language, feelings of information trends. From the above, we find that communication goes in two directions, as it affects the general atmosphere in which the communication process occurs, as it is a continuous and dynamic process, and communication is a social interaction between people that is affected by their conditions, culture, and environment.

⁴ See: Media and its contemporary theories: 41.

This process has several divisions, all of which revolve around the fact that the communication process is circular, as follows:

Made Means⁵:

- Readable means: such as newspapers, books, magazines, posters, booklets, guideboards, organizational guide and organizational charts, memoranda, rules and policies, and written administrative instructions and decisions.
- Audible means: such as radio and telephone.
- Audio-visual means: such as lectures, seminars, television, personal messenger (assigning someone to convey the message).
- Visual aids: such as galleries, pictures, sign language.

All these aforementioned means are of the old style, while the new style is done through the Internet space.

- Electronic means: They may contain audiovisual or readable means in the Internet, and social media.

Language of communication 6

1. Non-verbal communication: It is a communication process based on movements, behaviors, and other behaviors.

Research has indicated that non-verbal communication and behaviors make up 60–65% of interpersonal communication and communication. For example, a person's sharp and loud tone of voice or angry and stern facial expressions may have a message that others understand by decoding them as the person's dissatisfaction or frustration with the level of performance of subordinates. Silence in some situations may be more expressive than saying.

⁵-See: History of Communication and Media: 17

⁶- See: Administration and Business: 527

2. Verbal Communication: Verbal communication is the exchange of information using words.

One of the advantages of verbal communication is that it enhances the interaction between the sender and the receiver and allows for direct feedback, discussion and inquiry, and it also allows the transfer of a greater amount of information than in written communications. Verbal communication does not take much time and encourages collaboration and friendships. This method is also the most appropriate in the event that one of the parties to the communication does not know how to read and write, as well as when there is no need for codification and documentation, especially when the distances and good relations between the employees of the organization are close. However, one of its disadvantages is that oral information can be forgettable and difficult to document as evidence that can be consulted where witnesses are needed.

Size of call participants⁷:

- 1- Self-communication: It is a communication that takes place within the individual's mind, in which ideas and experiences are evaluated within the process of perception, and that is of interest to psychologists.
- 2- Personal communication: It is the communication that takes place between two or more people within the framework of forming relationships or exchanging experiences, as is the case today in social media platforms.
- 3- Group communication: It is a communication that occurs between a group linked by a communication situation, such as: family members, students, friends.... etc.
- 4- Public communication: It is the communication between two parties, one of which is the individual (the source) and the other is the group (the recipient), and it is often in formal or informal gatherings, such as lectures and seminars etc.
- 5- Intermediate communication: It is a communication made by closed circuits such as the telephone, through which two or more people with a communication goal communicate. It is called intermediate communication because it combines personal and mass communication, where the first is in terms of number, and the second in terms of means.

⁷- See: Communication and its Contemporary Theories: 29

- 6- Mass communication: It is the process that is carried out using mass media, which has several advantages, including: it is transcontinental, transcends the limits of time, and for all age groups, and its members do not meet directly, and its messages are controlled through the "gatekeeper", and there is almost no resonance.

Communication Barriers 8

❖ **Personal Barriers**

Personal obstacles are due to factors related to both the sender and the receiver, which include:

- Individual differences in terms of individuals' differing judgment, emotions, culture, values, and educational level.
- Selective understanding and cognition: where the individual sometimes tends to select the information he wants to hear and commensurate with what he believes and then interprets the message on this basis.
- Inability to formulate and encode the message appropriately by the sender or inability of the receiver to decode it correctly.
- The sender lacks writing or public speaking skills or the receiver lacks listening skills.
- Lack of credibility and trust between the sender and the receiver, which may lead to the message being neglected by the receiver for not trusting or respecting the sender.
- Intentional distortion of the facts and the meaning of the message by the receiver.

❖ **Technical Barriers**

They are constraints related to distance or time and include:

- The sender does not have enough time to understand the receiver or formulate the message appropriately.
- Distances, which may sometimes lead to an impact on the understanding of the message or being affected by it as it should be.

❖ **Organizational Barriers**

They are obstacles related to the lack of a clear communication structure and specific communication channels, including:

⁸-See: Administration and Business: 535

- Lack of an organizational structure that clearly defines the organization's formal lines of authority and specific communication channels, which confuses, for example, the employee who would like to contact their manager.
- The administration follows policies that discourage communication as in the case of autocratic/dictatorial leadership.
- Lack of an organizational unit through which data and information are collected, transferred and disseminated among the members of the organization.
- Lack of clarity of organizational policies, rules and procedures, which opens the way for personal interpretation, which leads to different understanding and visions among the members of the organization.
- Nomination or information portal: Failure to complete the communication process effectively is sometimes related to the presence of people who represent the link between the sender and the receiver, such as secretarial staff, who are called the information portal, where they sometimes filter (Filtering), i.e. shortening, neglecting or delaying the submission of messages to the manager, which negatively affects the process of delivering the message.

❖ **Environmental Barriers**

They are obstacles due to a set of factors related to the environment in which communication takes place, including:

- The factor of language and the variation of societies, customs, customs, and traditions.
- Lack of proper infrastructure such as lines of communication.
- Noise in the work environment, and the conditions of the work environment such as lighting, ventilation and overcrowding, which affects the general mood and focus and attention.
- Delay in transporting mail and letters due to the unavailability or efficiency of postal transport offices in the community.

Connection Steps⁹

1. The existence of an idea or information that must be transferred from one party (the sender) to another party (the receiver), meaning that there is a goal for communication.
2. The sender identifies the receiver and then crystallizes the idea and formulates it by the sender in a way that the receiver can understand (coding).
3. Choosing the communication channel that suits: the nature of the message, the sender, the receiver, and the environment in which the communication will be made.
4. Addressing confusion and obstacles that may hinder the delivery of the message in the required manner and at the appropriate time.
5. Send the message and make sure it arrives.
6. Receive the message from the future, decipher it, and understand its meaning and content.
7. Response and feedback by the receiver and reply to the message (the communication process is circular)

Functions of means of communication

Dr. Fadil Delew stated that the functions according to the programs and materials published by those means lie in the following¹⁰:

- 1- News Function
- 2- Recreational Function
- 3- The development function (regarding governments' understanding of their economic plans)

⁹- See: History of Communication and Media: 12

¹⁰- See: Previous source: 29

Phases of communication development¹¹

First: Audible communication:

The stage of audible communication began since ancient times when man knew the process of exchanging news, when he was blowing trumpets declaring a state of war or peace, or celebrating a religious occasion...etc.

Antiquity and a part of the Middle Ages also knew (the callers) who roamed the markets, and the places of other human gatherings; to inform (the parishioners) or citizens of the government's orders and statements.

In the Roman and Greek civilizations, epics and sermons were also famous, and among the Arabs before Islam, poetry prevailed among them as a language of discourse.

Second: Manuscript Communication:

There is no boundary between the historical stages that communication has gone through. The second stage consisted of engraving on stones, painting on temples and tombs, and writing papyrus, before four thousand years BC.

The European bourgeoisie historically began as a mercantile financial and then turned at the beginning of the ninth century into an industrial bourgeoisie, and this bourgeoisie established the liberal philosophy, as it was formed in news bulletins of interest to traders, where it was enshrined in several regions of Europe at the end of the Middle Ages.

This stage lasted for a long time after the appearance of printed communication after the discovery of the printing press. The establishment and spread of printing presses took a long time, and their emergence was accompanied by the monopoly of some governments on printing presses. Therefore, the writers and collectors of copied news maintained their sources of news and their customers for a long time, and after the appearance of the printer until 1789.

Third: Printed Communication:

The advent of printed communication was associated with the discovery of the printing press in the mid-15th century by John Gutenberg.

¹¹- Look: Modern means of communication from the newspaper to Facebook: 37 – 44

Manuscript newspapers, songs, photographs, calendars, calendar publications, and publications with astrological tendencies until the middle of the eighteenth century provided popular literature circulating among the popular classes, and until that time were often more effective than printed news.

But at the end of the eighteenth century, the news press wiped out these manuscript news styles. The spread of printing presses, the cheap price of news newspapers, and the high distribution of print from them led to the disappearance of the manuscript news altogether.

The spread of printed news bulletins was also helped by the increase in people's interest in colonial news after the era of geographical revelations, the Turkish and Italian wars, in which the majority of European countries participated, the emergence of Martin Luther's religious movement, the prosperity of the Renaissance, the control of the bourgeois class over European life, and the increase in democratic freedoms.

In general, we can observe four main factors behind the emergence and spread of printed communication in the modern era:

- The invention of the printing press, its role in increasing the number of copies, the newspaper's access to a large number of readers, saving effort, time and money.
- The emergence of the bourgeois class in Western Europe.
- The emergence of liberal thought in the bourgeois class.
- The establishment of postal services at the end of the fifteenth century, and the early sixteenth century, where its existence achieved the speed and organization of the access of newspapers to subscribers.

Fourth: Electronic Communication:

It is the stage that combined the previous stages, and used the media from audio and image.

These include the field of memorizing or recalling press information such as the use of film thumbnails, automated remote information processing systems, or in the field of collecting and printing press material such as the use of photographic collection systems, offset printing, computer use in press management, the emergence of the Internet, and the subsequent social media, and electronic newspapers.

Pillars of Communication¹²

Element 1: Sender

Definition: It is the source of the message according to multiple communication activities, all of which are focused on sending information, whether by word or code, whether confrontation or a specific means.

Its importance for other communication elements:

- 1- Message: The sender meets the interests of the receiver in the message he will address to him.
- 2- Means: The sender should be familiar with the arts of persuasion and the means of influencing others.
- 3- Receiver: The sender must know the directions and motives of the receiver.
- 4- Echo feedback: Allows the sender to read and understand the response and reaction of the receiver.

Use it: It is in three steps:

- 1- Familiarity with the subject: It is the availability of sufficient information, and the size of this subject depends on the nature of the communication situation, for example:

The communication attitude between husband and wife about choosing a picnic place; this does not require complexity and abundance of information, unlike other situations such as the preparation of news reports, or scientific research in which the researcher attends a master's or doctoral thesis.

- 2- Experience: It means the reference of the sender, as the health affairs spokesman is the doctor, and as another example, we note the keenness of toothpaste promoters to wear the advertising representative as a doctor. This means that the speaker forms a high reference stemming from knowledge of the thing.

¹²-See: Modern means of communication from the newspaper to Facebook: 52 – 63

3- Communication skills: It includes the ability of the sender to use all influential means from the moment the message is sent to the future, until he gets what he wants from the future.

Relationship to other elements:

1- Message: Its relationship with the sender lies in the credibility of the sender, making it influential.

2- Receiver: By the sender's credibility, the sender obtains the trust of the receiver, and this relationship is reflected in the receiver's delivery of the content of the message and being affected by it.

3- Means: The level of means to be used by the sender varies according to his physical and mental abilities.

4- Echo return: It helps the sender to modify the message according to the nature of the communication situation.

Element 2: Message

Definition: Everything that is transmitted and exchanged between the sender and the receiver of information, whether verbal or non-verbal.

Relevance to other elements:

1- Sender: He is the creator of the message, and the sender of it.

2-The means: The means can only be determined in the form of the message. If the message is read, its means will be written (newspapers), and if the message is viewed, the means will be visible (television), and so on.

3-The future: The message must be formulated in an appropriate manner to ensure that the meaning reaches the future.

4- Reverberation: It is possible to modify the message to suit the need of the future.

Use it: in three steps:

1- Code: It is the way in which symbols are formed, whether verbal or non-verbal.

2- Content: Here begins the construction of the content of the message.

3- Processing: commensurate with the rest of the communication elements.

Relationship to other elements:

1-The sender: The message means to him that every word or act of man carries meaning to others.

2- Means: The mission plays an economic, temporal, spatial and human role in determining the level of means.

3-The future: It has the burden of understanding the message, and deciphering it.

4- Echo returned: Modifying the message may be quick and less expensive if the echo returned quickly depending on the communication situation, for example:

If we have a university professor giving a lecture, the students did not understand his purpose. If someone asks him about it, he will directly modify his message for the students to understand, according to the feedback. The modification may be in the content or code and then process and send it, unlike television programs. The modification is slow in the absence of means of communication with the program such as SMS, and others.

The third element: the means (Channel)¹³

Definition: It is the channel that carries the message or its meanings and conveys it to others, and it is called the mediator.

Relevance to other elements:

1-The sender: The sender is keen to acquire the appropriate means to deliver his message to whoever he wants, and he can also improve in choosing it according to the quality of the means and the extent of its ability to disseminate the message. An example would be a

If we have an important and useful video presenter, there are ways to deliver that message: YouTube, LiveStream, optical discs, television broadcasts.

2- Message: The means may be multiplied according to the type of message, for example:

¹³-See: History of Communication and Media: 22

The audio message can be sent via audio, visual and electronic means for the possibility of providing the means of listening. Among these means: MMS Mobile - Internet - Radio - Television.

3- Receiver: When communication scholars divided the forms of communication, the focus was on the means because it is the difference between the forms of communication in determining the size of the receivers of the message according to the need of the sender and the message.

4- Echo return: It is not possible to know the echo return without the intermediary between the sender and the receiver "the means"; the world of communication "Wolber Schram" saw that the communication process is circular and goes in two directions.

Use it: in three steps:

1- Taking into account the circumstances and nature of the communication situation.

2- Choosing the appropriate type of communication for the medium, on three types: verbal - non-verbal - technical.

3- Eliminating any interference to the means, which disrupts the communication between the sender and the receiver. and confusion of three types: semantic - environmental - mechanical.

Relationship to other elements:

1- Sender: Where the sender bears the economic cost of that medium, such as radio or television broadcasting, paper press, electronic press, or lecture hall and its preparation.

2- The message: Where the message has an economic cost according to the absorption of the means of the number of recipients, for example:

If we have a government entity that uses SMS mobile, the cost will be calculated on the number of messages for the cadres in that entity that absorbs them.

3-The receiver: The medium made the receiver and the sender exchange roles, so that the sender is a receiver, and the receiver is a sender.

4- Echo return: The means is a channel for communicating the response of the receiver to the sender.

Element 4: Receiver

Its definition: It is the recipient of the message sent by the source, and the recipient may be a “face-to-face communication” individual, or several “mass communication” individuals.

Its importance to other elements:

1-The sender: The importance of the receiver is equal to the importance of the sender in the communication process, as he listens, thinks, reacts and responds.

2-The message: The effect of the message is not known unless it knows who the receiver is, and how it interacts with the sender.

3- Method: The evaluation of the method knows the extent of listening and responding to the future.

4- Echo return: Echo return does not come unless the receiver understands all elements of communication.

Use it: in three steps:

1- Listen to the message and decode it.

2. Provide a critical vision of the future of the mission.

3-The sender shares the feeling through the response.

Relationship to other elements:

1- Sender: The relationship of the receiver with the sender is a dynamic relationship in the exchange of information.

2. Message: Makes the future a messenger.

3- Means: From the point of view of the receiver, maintaining or upgrading the communication through the means means means that he is interested in the elements of communication, but if he stops communicating by the means, this is evidence of his lack of acceptance of this, for example:

If we have a television competition program, and one of the program's authors texted to participate in the program via text messages, they told him that participating by phone

enhances his winning more prizes, and that his personal presence will give him the opportunity to win immediately, while SMS has prizes by lottery. If he has a strong propensity to profit, he will participate in the audience, and if he is cautious about the credibility of the channel, he may not participate at all.

4- Reverberation: It is a response that the message leaves with the receiver, and it produces a certain effect from the receiver towards the sender.

Element 5: Feed back

Definition: All that the receiver does towards the sender in response to his message after being affected by that message.

Its importance to other elements:

1- Sender: The echo return is a recommendation if the receiver wishes to continue communicating with the sender.

2- Message: With the return of the echo, the sender and the receiver can exchange ideas and information.

3- Means: Echo feedback helps maintain or improve the means. Abbreviations: ASG, Assistant Secretary-General

If a teacher threw a lesson at a group of students by the book, he did not absorb some of the intended students, so he resorted to the projector screen to display the visual information, so they understood it, so he upgraded the means, or canceled the book and started explaining it by forming groups and ordered them to certain activities in order to absorb the message, so he canceled the means.

4-The receiver: The echo returned queen in the hand of the receiver, and the message is queen in the hand of the sender.

Use it: in three steps:

1-To know the identity and directions of the sender.

2- Forming verbal / nonverbal code to express acceptance or rejection of the message.

3- Sending it directly to the sender as in "personal confrontational" communication, or by means of "mass" communication.

Relationship to other elements:

- 1-The sender: returns the echo to the conviction, or tries to obtain his request in another way.
- 2- Message: It helps to modify the message according to the nature of the communication situation.
- 3- Means: The arrival of the echo back to the sender varies according to the form of communication (personal - public).
- 4- Receiver: Helps to show their participation and interaction with the sender.

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